

A Critical Analysis of Legislative Measures for Startups in India in Digital Era

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The success of the young entrepreneur will be the key to India's transformation in the new Millennium.

-Dhirubhai Ambani

India is a developing country and its economy is growing at a fast pace. There has been a rapid increase in startups as the Government of India is focusing more on innovation. The researchers focus on the regulations in India and compare them with those in Dubai and Singapore. The research shall examine various compliances to be done by the startups in India and the regulations to be followed by them. The study undertakes a comparison of the regulations prevailing in India with those in Dubai and Singapore. She will also be focusing on the legal factors affecting startups. The study is structured with two objectives and a single research hypothesis. The researcher will be examining the regulatory framework governing the startups in India, and evaluating whether India is startup friendly country. The researcher shall be testing whether people are aware of the laws governing the startups.

Keywords : Innovation, fast pace, startups, Governing, Legal.

Introduction

The startup ecosystem has grown in India due to funding by the government. Nowadays, the government has more focus on innovation. Innovation attracts the patent. The Government of India is focusing more on the registration of patents. Innovation is the asset of the startup. The campaign of the startup was 1st announced by Hon'ble Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi in his speech on 15th August, 2015. This initiative is a kind of an action plan in order to develop the ecosystem related to these innovations to promote and nurture entrepreneurship in India. The Government of India has been taking continuous steps by implementing various schemes to promote new entrepreneurs so that they can start new ventures.

In order to be eligible for the startup schemes, any enterprise should not be formed by way of reconstruction or by splitting and at the same time should not have exceeded the turnover of Rs.100crores since its existence. The startups are reachable effectively to outreach because of the digital era. With the increasing use of technology there have been many startups focusing on the use Artificial intelligence.

Indian startups prefer going abroad and doing their business. If seen carefully, it's a race where Singapore and Dubai are running faster than India and competing with us. They have become a formidable competitor of India. If seen, Indian Brands register themselves in Dubai and Singapore. Several Indian startups have opted for incorporation in foreign countries, e.g., brands like Meesho, MPL, Zepto, Phonepe, Flipkart and Mobi due to taxation and regulations.

Research Objectives

1. To critically examine the regulatory framework governing startups in India, while keeping in mind the focus on innovation in India.
2. To evaluate whether India is startup friendly country.
3. To suggest an appropriate major for the effective implementation of startups initiatives in India.

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Hypothesis

There is a lack of awareness among the people on laws governing startups in India, various relaxations and exemptions on taxes that apply to them.

Research Gap

Although in India the startups have been recognised as well as supported with various initiative was taken by the government by starting the “Startup India initiative”. However, the existing literature review focuses on the formation of the startup and not on the survival of the startups. The researcher will address these issues and understand the regulations and benefits in the other countries as compared to India.

Currently, the literature available focuses on the incubation phase and early-stage funding. There is a research gap regarding the "Exit and Reverse Flip" legislation, focusing on the legal complexities which are involved when Indian startups attempt to move their headquarters back to India (*Ghar Wapsi karne ke liye*) or list on domestic versus international exchanges under the latest 2025-26 regulations.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a research design which is comprising doctrinal legal research and empirical analysis. Primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire from founders of startups, professionals and businessmen, while secondary data is collected from sources including books, statutes, judicial decisions, papers and articles. To develop a coherent theoretical framework relevant to the subject under examination. In addition, the empirical dimension of the research is carried out through a questionnaire method. Data are collected from 50 sample respondents.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Only 18% people are aware about the key laws governing the startups. A combined 48 % heard of them or are not aware at all. While only 26 % people completely “not aware about the startup India initiative and legal benefits and relaxation and 42 % people have heard about it but never explored. 64 % people are not aware about the tax exemptions or incentives available to startups. Only 6 % are fully aware and have applied. The tax incentives are the important part of the startups but the awareness about the same is negligible. If seen few people have heard the name of these regulations but there is a lack of the in-depth knowledge about the same. 32 % finds it difficult to do compliance of legal. 30 % people stated that they require professional advice for doing compliance, this proves that the laws in India are not startup friendly and compliances are difficult thus they need to take professional advice. 54% people never thought of taking funding under the scheme. The reason being lack of awareness 50 % people have stated that they are neutral about India’s been a startup friendly country. The above data collected suggests that people are somewhat aware about the startup rules however there is a gap in the knowledge, it seems that people have not explored these areas. Thus, the hypothesis is hence proved.

Laws in India Compared with Other Countries

The legal framework that governs startups in India is very recent compared to other countries. India’s regulations are still at the developing stage and countries like Dubai and Singapore have robust legislation and they have evolved over the decades. There is no single and consolidated statutes/law that exclusively governs startups in India. Instead, startups are regulated through multiple laws viz company law, tax law, labour laws, intellectual property laws and foreign investment policies.

On the other hand, many developed countries have a streamlined regulatory mechanism that is specifically tailored to support startups and innovation-driven enterprises. For example, Singapore offers a very simplified business registration process, attractive tax incentives, and clear regulatory guidance for new businesses and Dubai is also rapidly increasing and giving a free zone for tax benefits. The Main focus of this country is reducing compliance burdens and creating a predictable legal environment, which helps startups scale more efficiently without any hurdles.

For Recognising the importance of entrepreneurship in India for economic growth, the Government has taken significant steps in recent years to strengthen the startup ecosystem. One of the most notable initiatives taken by the government is the start of the *Startup India* scheme, under which startups are officially recognised by the Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT). This recognition helps the eligible startups to avail various benefits such as tax

exemptions, easier compliance norms, faster patent examination and access to government funding and incubation support.

Indian Regulations for Startups

In India, startups are governed by the following laws

- 1) The Companies Act, 2013: In India, Indian startups are governed by the Companies Act, 2013.
- 2) The Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999 (FEMA)
- 3) Income Tax Act, 1961.
- 4) The Central Goods and Services Tax Act, 2017
- 5) Further, in addition, if the startups want to work in a regulated sector, they have to comply with various laws and obtain the mandatory license as well as approval from various authorities like the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI), Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDAI), depending on the nature of their business.

Compliance for Registration of a Company

In India, if anyone wants to register a company than they have to register themselves under the Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA). Additionally, they have to apply for the following viz:

-) Permanent Account Number (PAN),
-) Tax Deduction and Collection Account Number (TAN) for company incorporation
-) Even if they have to get a GST number after receiving the PAN number.
-) Additionally, they have to apply separately in the Provident Fund (PF),
-) Employees' State Insurance Corporation (ESIC) and professional tax laws.

This incorporation process is very complex and time-consuming for a newly startups. If there is any foreign ownership in a startup than they have to comply with FEMA laws also. This reflects that Indian laws are complex and not startup-friendly. Further in India, it is also not easy to register under startup India scheme by DPIIT.

For every startup in India, they have to comply with the following:

-) File companies' audit yearly,
-) Income Tax Audit (subject to turnover),
-) File GST return every month,
-) File PF returns every month and
-) Professional Tax returns and
-) File yearly Income Tax Return.

In case the startup is regulated by specific laws viz SEBI, RBI, then they have to do additional compliance.

Further, even after registering the Startup in India, Post Incorporation Compliance are more complex. They are more likely to get deeper scrutiny in various departments and laws post-incorporation.

They also have to comply with various separate Laws and Regulations according to their nature of business, RBI Regulation for Fintech, FEMA for Foreign Funding. Even though there are separate State Specific Laws which also have to be complied with according to the governing State laws in which they are registered.

Abolition of Angel Tax (Section 56(2)(viib) Income Tax Act, which came into effect on 1st April 2025: A landmark move has been taken by the government of India in 2024-25 that has removed the tax on capital which is raised above "fair market value," significantly easing the burden on early-stage valuations.¹

Key Legal Factors Related to the Growth of Startups in India

-) **Issues related to Intellectual Property Rights in India:** The Indian startups that are creative or technology-driven frequently faces challenge drelating to Intellectual Property Rights. Issues related to it arises any many occasions due to a lack of awareness about the criteria for filing a patent, the complex procedure to be followed, the patent and the time for getting the grant of a patent. The one dealing with any software created with the help of artificial intelligence also faces ambiguity about the ownership.
The Government of India had taken the initiative to expedite patent application alongwith giving concessions on fees for startups recognised by DPIIT. However, due to a lack of knowledge about the said initiative, there is less utilisation of IPR in our country, which is affecting innovation and competitiveness.
-) **Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Restrictions:** A few sectors have got 100% FDI; however other are subject to conditions and approval by the government. Due to complexities in understanding the FDI eligibility, compliance with guidelines related to pricing, restrictions in sectors, it becomes necessary to take professional advice, which increases the cost and time, which is detrimental for the growth of innovation.
-) **Complexity of the Judicial and Dispute Resolution Process:** In India, we have a robust legal system but, the procedure is very complex. The legal cases are time-consuming and also cost involved are high, which is a challenge faced by the startup. Due to limited human and financial resources, it becomes difficult to pursue the legal complications or cases relating to contracts, intellectual property infringement, shareholder conflicts, etc. Due to a lack of judicial mechanisms specifically dealing with cases and issues of startups and due to prolonged commercial cases, startups get discouraged from asserting their legal rights. Thus, they resort to out-of-court settlements and avoid litigation, which gives rise to compromise.
-) **Taxation:** In India, new ventures are liable to pay approximately 22% corporate tax under the Income Tax laws. In India Government has given the exemption to recognised startups u/s 80IAC of the Income Tax Act, but this is subject to the approval from the Income Tax department after making an application. The said exemptions are for any 3 consecutive years out of 10 years. In India, ESOP (Employees stop option) is taxable under Salary as a perquisite and it is taxable at the time of sale of shares as Capital Gain.²

Various Government Scheme for India Startups

SEED Fund Scheme: The Government of India has launched the Startup India SEED fund scheme, where companies can apply for the grant and investment support under the Startup India scheme. The startup should not be more than two years old and it should be a private limited, limited liability partnership (LLP), or partnership firm with a minimum 51 % holding by an Indian. The idea should be innovative for attracting a grant or investment from the government. The maximum size of a grant from the government is 20 lakhs and the maximum size of investment from the government will be 51 lakhs via debt or debenture.³

For applying for this scheme, it is necessary to keep in mind that the startup should not have already been taken benefit of any other government scheme and/or received grant of more than 10 lakh from that scheme.

Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises scheme (CGTMSE)

The Central government has launched this scheme for startups, where the startup can apply for a loan of 20 crores from a bank or a Non-Banking Financial Company (NBFC) without providing any security or collateral. Under this scheme, the bank can sanction the loan for the working capital requirement or Capex (capital expenditure)⁴. For availing this scheme, the startup should not have defaulted on any loan in the past⁵. Under this scheme, the Government provides 75% to 85% guarantee cover.⁶

Patent scheme: In India, the Government have fast tracked the startup patent application. The startup will be getting 80% rebate in filing fees for a patent, compared to other business provided

you should be having DPIIT certificate for startups. The Government has also made a panel of facilitator in assisting in the filing of IP applications for startups.⁷ Patent application is typical and facilitatory helps in assisting the patent. The Government of India is giving exemptions in many tenders regarding the turnover criteria and also the relaxation in EMD (Earnest Money Deposit). The State Government is simultaneously having various schemes for startups in India, like SEED funding, electricity subsidy, stamp duty exemption etc.

To summarize, the Government of India has taken various steps to encourage startups and entrepreneurship in India by providing various schemes at the central as well as state level⁸.

India's startup system is the world's largest startup ecosystem, where more than 2 lakhs startups have been recognised and registered as of 31-12-2025. Out of which 50% startups are registered from Tier 2 cities and Tier 3 cities of India, which is motivating entrepreneurship in small cities also. India's startup ecosystem has generated more than 21 lakhs jobs, where 45% startups have atleast one-woman partner.⁹

"In India in 2014, there were only 4 privately held companies, which were valued at \$1 billion, and now the valuation is more than \$ 350 billion, consisting of 120 firms. Till now, the Government has approved the corpus to the tune of 945 crores for 215 incubators to support early-stage startups. The Government has launched the Startup India Investor connect portal with the help of SIDBI. The platform that connects startups with venture capital funds (VC), investors etc., through a single application"¹⁰.

Law of Singapore

Singapore is Asia's first startup-friendly and investor friendly country¹¹. Singapore's laws are startup friendly and stable. Singapore is the first preferred jurisdiction for global investors, holding companies or regional headquarters in Asia. It is the global and financial hub of Asia, as it has very minimal statutory compliances viz company incorporation and related compliances, which are a single window operation for corporate entities. Singapore's laws are globally aligned laws and very transparent laws.¹²

In Singapore, the company gets incorporated within a single day with \$ 1, and there is no restriction on the cap of foreign shareholding, there is also no sectoral cap also so foreign investor prefers to invest in Singapore freely. Even the startups in Singapore are most attractive startups worldwide. The compliance is very low for the startups and there is an audit exemption to them.¹³

Singapore Taxation

The Singapore Government has given an exemption with a cap for taxation for early year and the tax rate is only 17% and there is no dividend tax or capital gain tax. The Singapore is ESOP friendly country; thus, founders prefer to set up the company there¹⁴.

Startup schemes:

In Singapore, the Government never invests alone in early-stage startups they prefer to invest with a private investor and it reduces its risk. The government of Singapore gives the grant in the deep tech and IP. Maximin grant size is S\$ 400K in case of Proof of Concept(POC)and Proof of value (POV), they give S\$ 800k grant¹⁵.

The Government also supports startups with mentorship, investor access, and office space with the help of an incubator. In Singapore, the legal disputes are resolved on fast-track dispute resolution mechanism and there is more reliance placed on resolving disputes through arbitration. It is very easy for the investor to take exists or transfer of share or any overseas listing of the company. Thus, Singapore is termed the most friendly for new business.

Law of Dubai

Dubai is a tech efficient country where the government has recently incorporated the corporate tax in the Dubai mainland. There are lots of zones like FTZ (free trade zone) where there is NIL corporation tax. Dubai is investor friendly country and there is no personal taxation, thus it attracts many founders to build their startups. It has a duopoly legal system which, includes

the UAE civil law and respective FTZ laws. In Dubai, the incorporation of a company is quick with the minimum ownership restrictions in the Dubai mainland and no restriction on FTZ¹⁶. There is very little regulatory intervention, it is also a startup and investor friendly company due to low taxation. Dubai has emerged as a holding company structured by the startups for getting investment from the VC¹⁷. Dubai's common law is very effective and quick.¹⁸

In Dubai, the government has also launched various schemes for promoting startups via grants and loans¹⁹. To summarise, the following are the reasons why Indian startups prefer registration of their business in Singapore and Dubai.²⁰

Sr No.	Particulars	India	Singapore	Dubai
1	Corporate Tax system	25%	17%	9%
2	Chinese Funding	Approval from RBI and government of India required	Easy and high funding	Rapid growth as compared to India
3	Rank For Ease of Doing Business by Embassy of India, The Hague and Netherlands	63 rd Rank	2 nd rank	16 th rank
4	Capital Gain Tax	15-20 %	0%	0% personal income tax and 0% capital gain on investment
5	Intellectual Property Laws	Complex laws and time consuming	Robust and fast track laws, transparent laws	Free zone protection
6	Arbitration	Length and time consuming	International trusted	Quick resolution
7	Startup Eco System	It is growing but still developing	Matured and investor driven	It's an innovation hub and developing

Failure of startup rates in India:

According to the Institute of Business Value and Oxford Economics, more than 90% startups fail in the initial 5 years of launching, the main reason of startup failure is due to lack of funds, insufficient product demand, huge competition, founder disputes and inadequate mentoring²¹.

In India in 2025, as per the study, there were 11,223 startups that failed in the first 10 months from their launch.²² Various startups have failed in 2024, viz. Stao (Edtech), Goldpe (Fintech), Nintee (Healthcare), my Tirth India (Spiritual Tech)²³

The statistics of the startups that failed during the last few years are as follows:²⁴

Sr No	Years	Startups closed
1	2025	259
2	2024	12,717 startups closed
3	2023	15,921 startups closed
4	2019-2022	9,600 annually

Earlier, it was easy to get funding for startups; each and all projects were funded and funding was easier even if they did not survive. However, nowadays getting funds has become very difficult; there are no self-sustaining systems.

Union Budget 2026

The Union Budget 2026 has shifted its focus from creating an ecosystem for deepening the ecosystem. The 2026 budget provides for a massive capital to high tech sectors, same time it the ease of doing business remained untouched and debatable.

In the budget Government has given importance to Deep-Tech & Research & Development the Anusandhan Pivot and now Rs. 1 lakh crore funds will be deployed in an annual installment of Rs.20,000/- . This shift in tax is similar to the model followed in Singapore Temasek²⁵. Also, extension in recognition from 10 years to 15 years, which will help the companies to survive in the long term and get tax benefits for an additional 5 years.

Conclusion

Indian startup laws are now far better than 10 years ago, yet needs a lot of improvisation with respect to taxation laws, compliance, audits, their FDI norms and even Indian laws should be investor-friendly like Singapore, Dubai, so that India can attract more foreign investments.

Although these initiatives mark a positive progress towards encouraging the startups, challenges remain the same in terms of complex laws and their implementation. Indian startups often face compliance requirements from multiple authorities, which is termed as time-consuming and costly, especially during the early stages of their growth. If compared to countries that are more mature with respect to startup laws, India is still developing and in the process of creating a balanced legal framework that would encourage innovation while ensuring regulatory oversight.

Overall, while India's startup laws are not yet as developed or unified as those in some other countries, the ongoing policy reforms and government support indicate a strong commitment toward fostering entrepreneurship and innovation. The vision of "Vikshit Bharat" and GIFT city and other policies, schemes continue to evolve, India's legal environment for startups is expected to become more structured, transparent and globally competitive.

Suggestions

-) India should bring one window system where a startup can easily get a grant or a loan from the state or central government, get connected to an investor, mentorship, compliances and other requirements related to startups.
-) India government should also bring more transparency in startup funding in their incubation so that there will be more success rates than failures.
-) Even India government should also give preference in government tenders, government supplies to startups so that they can easily survive in the market.
-) The Government should fast track legal system governing startups and funds should be made available easily under various schemes.
-) The Government should monitor and track the survival of these startups.
-) Tax compliance should be simplified.
-) Relaxations on labour laws compliance.
-) Create awareness about the startups and legal education for the same should be provided.
-) The approval process for getting foreign funding should be simplified.
-) Fast-track dispute resolution mechanism.
-) Free zones for startups should be encouraged.
-) Assistance should be provided to startups to survive at a global level and also provide global networking platforms.

References

-) The Companies Act, 2013
-) The Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999 (FEMA)
-) Income Tax Act, 1961.
-) The Central Goods and Services Tax Act, 2017
-) “*Taxation of Start-ups*”, Publisher Taxmann, Month & Year of Publication March 2025, 8th Edition, ISBN No.9789364550864.
-) Vinay Vaish, “India Business Guide Startup to Set-up”, ISBN- 9789356037946, Edition-September 2025, publisher Commercial Law Publishers.
-) CS Amit Baxi, “*MSME & Start Ups Law & Practice*”, tax publisher, Edition 2024

Webliography

-) www.financialexpress.com
-) www.economicstimes.indiatimes.com
-) www.theindiajobs.com
-) www.counselindia.com
-) www.tice.news
-) www.explore-dubai.com
-) www.executivecentre.com
-) www.mof.gov.sg
-) www.startupindia.gov.in
-) www.nimsme.gov.in
-) www.khuranaandkhurana
-) www.taxguru.in
-) www.seedfund.startupindia.gov.in

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1. [https://www.startupindia.gov.in/content/sih/en/startupgov/regulatory_updates.html#:~:text=2\)%202024%20removed%20Section%2056,August%202024,accessed on 11-12-2025 at 1pm](https://www.startupindia.gov.in/content/sih/en/startupgov/regulatory_updates.html#:~:text=2)%202024%20removed%20Section%2056,August%202024,accessed on 11-12-2025 at 1pm)
 2. <https://taxguru.in/income-tax/taxation-framework-startups-india.html>, accessed on 12-12-2025 at 12 pm.
 3. <https://seedfund.startupindia.gov.in/>, accessed on 12-12-2026 at 1pm.
 4. <https://www.nimsme.gov.in/about-scheme/credit-guarantee-fund-trust-for-micro-and-small-enterprises-cgtmse->
 5. Notification by Ministry of commerce and industry, new Delhi, 8th May, 2025, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 12 pm
 6. <https://www.startupindia.gov.in/content/sih/en/credit-guarantee-scheme-for-startups.html>, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 2 pm
 7. <https://www.khuranaandkhurana.com/2025/01/27/dpiit-patent-schemes-for-startups>, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 3 pm
 8. <https://www.startupindia.gov.in/content/sih/en/startup-scheme.html>, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 4 pm
 9. Report by Ministry of Commerce & Industry on Startup India Has Evolved into a Defining Movement of New India: Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi released on 16 Jan,2026
 10. https://www.pib.gov.in/PressNoteDetails.aspx?ModuleId=3&NoteId=156949&lang=1®=3&utm_source
 11. <https://quickbooks.intuit.com/sg/r/starting-a-business/intuit-quickbooks-asia-startup-index/>
 12. <https://bizsquare.com.sg/why-singapore-is-the-best-place-to-start-a-business-in-asia/>
 13. <https://www.executivecentre.com/en-in/blog-article/singapore-limited-liability-company-registration-cost-requirement/>

-
14. <https://www.mof.gov.sg/policies/taxes/corporate-income-tax/>
 15. <https://www.fi-group.sg/grants/startup-sg-tech>, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 5 pm
 16. <https://explore-dubai.com/blog/dubais-tech-pulse-2025-and-beyond-how-the-city-is-shaping-tomorrow/>, accessed on 13-12-2025 at 6 pm
 17. <https://dartuae.com/blog/complete-guide-to-dubai-business-friendly-laws>, accessed on 14-12-2025 at 11 am
 18. https://dubai-businesscapital.com/post_articles/dubai-the-rising-star-of-global-startups-and-innovation/, accessed on 14-12-2025 at 12 pm
 19. <https://focus.hidubai.com/support-fchator-startups-and-smes/>, accessed on 14-12-2025 at 1 pm
 20. <https://www.tice.news/tice-trending/why-are-indian-startups-moving-their-hqs-to-singapore-dubai-8763609>, accessed on 14-12-2025 at 2 pm
 21. https://www.counselindia.com/blog-detail/the-percentage-of-startups-failing-in-india-?utm_source, accessed on 15-12-2025 at 12 pm
 22. <https://www.theindiajobs.com/blog/why-startups-fail-in-india/>, accessed on 15-12-2025 at 12 pm
 23. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/startups/shutting-shop-a-roundup-of-indian-startups-which-couldnt-survive-2025/articleshow/126182230.cms?from=mdr>, accessed on 15-12-2025 at 12 pm
 24. <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/start-ups/startup-shutdowns-increase-12-fold/3819797/>, accessed on 15-12-2025 at 1 pm
 25. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/science/budget-2025-rs-20000-crore-allocated-to-dst-to-kickstart-rs-1-lakh-crore-research-and-development-fund/articleshow/117836514.cms>, accessed on 15-12-2025 at 2 pm
